

**TRAINING
OPPORTUNITIES**

HORIZON EUROPE
NOVAFOODIES

We are seeking companies in the aquaculture sector to participate in the training courses offered by the NOVAFOODIES project

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 101084180.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

NOVAFOODIES is an innovative project aimed at developing new functional products derived from **marine and freshwater sources**, **utilizing more sustainable production methods** while maintaining sectoral competitiveness. The project will also focus on enhancing consumer trust through research on **product traceability and monitoring the environmental impact** of production processes.

TRAINING COURSES

NOVAFOODIES also seeks to **enhance workforce skills** through an engaging training program designed to deepen knowledge of the aquaculture sector. This program targets both **professionals and unemployed individuals**, equipping them with the competencies and skills needed to support this rapidly growing industry.

BENEFICIARIES OF THE TRAINING

AQUACULTURE COMPANIES

- Benefit from a tailored training program and gain access to a more diverse and skilled workforce.
- Establish strong collaborative networks with leading universities, R&D centers, and companies, contributing to scientific advancement.
- Foster inclusive practices and create a more equitable work environment, enhancing your company's reputation and attracting top talent.

WORK FORCE

- Gain valuable expertise and competencies while staying informed about new trends and innovative methodologies in aquaculture.
- Explore entrepreneurial opportunities and emerging market trends within the aquaculture sector.
- Benefit from a more inclusive environment and improved gender balance in decision-making roles.

UNEMPLOYED PEOPLE

- Receive training in aquaculture and sustainability, facilitating access to job opportunities in this growing sector.
- Become an active driver of the transition towards a more sustainable aquaculture industry.
- Enhance chances of securing sustainable employment and benefit from equal career opportunities.

TRAINING CURRICULUM

Production and processing techniques for marine and algae products within the context of sustainability.

Aquaculture system management and sustainability, including the species involved and fish nutrition.

Guidance on employment and entrepreneurship in response to current business trends and key sectors.

Gender equality in the sector, ensuring equal representation and access to decision-making processes.

Legal requirements and quality management related to novel and functional food legislation, safety, and traceability.

Future challenges and the significance of aquaculture within the broader context of food production and the blue economy.

METHODOLOGY

CLASSROOM SETTING

ON-SITE VISITS

E-LEARNING PLATFORM

WORKSHOPS

TIMELINE

**MAY-JUNE
2025**

ONLINE FOCUS GROUPS SESSIONS

Interested companies will participate in online focus group sessions with the consortium to learn in detail about the objectives and benefits of the training courses

**SEP-DEC
2025**

PILOT TRAINING COURSES

The NOVAFOODIES consortium will conduct simultaneous pilot training courses in Spain, Ireland, Greece, and China to assess the outcomes.

**JANUARY
2026**

REVIEW AND SCALING UP

After the completion of the pilot courses, companies will have the opportunity to share their feedback and to integrate the training program into their methodology.

HOW TO APPLY

If you are a company or a professional in the aquaculture sector, or if you are seeking job opportunities in this rapidly growing industry, please contact us at:

- Carlos Alonso: caleal@accioncontraelhambre.org
- Lisa Meidl: lisa.meidl@lva.at

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OUR TEAM

NOVAFOODIES is an innovative project developed by leading RTD centres, universities, companies, associations, and NGOs from Europe, Israel, and China.

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